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Enriching learning experiences for students to enhance their engineering competences across cultures and nations

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ABSTRACT

Engineers nowadays should be able to live and work in a global community across cultures and nations. Therefore they need to have broad engineering skills and know-how, be flexible and mobile, and be able to communicate, collaborate and interact in an international environment. But, where, when and how do they acquire these competences? This paper presents an example of a course, offered jointly by the Engineering Leadership Development Program at Penn State University (US) and the Postgraduate Program on Innovation and Entrepreneurship for Engineers at KU Leuven (Belgium). This course, entitled ‘Engineering Across Cultures and Nations’ at PSU and ‘Professional and Cross-cultural Skills in Engineering’ at KU Leuven, runs now since 2015. The course material is fully available online. Based on a flipped classroom model, each week the students have to study one of the online modules and come prepared to the face-to-face sessions. These joint sessions are held synchronously both in KU Leuven and in PSU once a week via a webconferencing tool. Each week students rotate responsibility for leading this classroom discussion. The course also incorporates substantial project work, that students work on in mixed virtual teams, using proper communication and collaboration tools, tackling challenges of different languages, time zones, engineering backgrounds, etc. Over the years the course components (learning approach, materials and activities) have been improved, in order to enhance and enrich the intercultural and international learning experiences for the students (and for the teachers).

INTRODUCTION

Engineers nowadays should be able to live and work in a professional, agile way in our contemporary global community, across cultures and nations. They not only need to have broad engineering skills and know-how, but should also be flexible and mobile, and be able to live and work internationally. In today’s global marketplace,

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successful engineers must combine their technical expertise with an understanding of how professionals in different cultures define problems and develop solutions.

To prepare future engineers for these new professional challenges, engineering educators are integrating genuine learning experiences in the curricula for engineering students to develop their intercultural competences. At The Pennsylvania State University (PSU) these skills and experiences have evolved since 1995 into a critical part of the undergraduate minor in the Engineering Leadership Development program (ELD). Over the past years the ELD program at PSU has been developing a Master of Engineering program to provide a graduate degree in Engineering Leadership and Innovation Management. The program developers recognize the importance of these global competencies at the graduate level as well as the undergraduate levels, and decided to incorporate an international virtual teaming course as a requirement in the program. In 2013-2014 they contacted KU Leuven in Belgium to establish a partnership in this endeavor. At KU Leuven the Faculty of Engineering Technology is organizing an annual Postgraduate Program on Innovation and Entrepreneurship in Engineering. This one-year program aims at developing entrepreneurial, managerial and innovation skills and offers the students an opportunity to gain a unique work experience through innovative projects in a stimulating working and learning environment. The match with the ambitions of the ELD program was obvious, and this led to the development of a common course, called *Engineering Across Cultures and Nations* at PSU and *Professional and Cross-cultural Skills in Engineering* at KU Leuven. This course is offered for students at both sides, since the academic year 2015-2016.

COURSE CHARACTERISTICS

General description

This graduate-level course focuses on the primary knowledge areas and essential competencies required for successful engineers to live and work in today's global marketplace. The course examines individual and cultural differences and how they impact business practices, communication and team dynamics when solving engineering problems in global contexts. These topics are central to international and multicultural engineering teams. The course takes the students on a journey from personal professional skills introspection and development towards intercultural and team competencies development. Students that complete the course will be able to understand sources of conflict that can arise in multicultural teams and effectively use the tools and resources learned in class to manage individual and team motivation and minimize or effectively deal with conflict, while harvesting the benefits of diversity as they work on a real world virtual team project, producing effective solutions to challenging engineering problems.

Course objectives

Upon completion of this course, students will be able to:

- Demonstrate a proficiency in team-building, leadership, and service in the context of cross-cultural engineering teams.
- Construct creative solutions to engineering issues incorporating cultural differences among team members and external stakeholders.
- Critically analyze personal and team-member competencies and biases.
- Formulate and apply strategies to improve engineering team dynamics.
- Provide effective feedback, recognition, motivation, and corrective guidance for international/intercultural team members.
- Evaluate engineering business opportunities or strategies for the diffusion of ideas within international and cross-cultural markets.
- Examine moral, ethical, and legal dilemmas in cross-cultural engineering environments.

Course contents

The top five most important attributes identified by industry leaders and engineering educators for global competence in engineering graduates are [1]:

- 1) An appreciation of other cultures,
- 2) Proficiency working in or directing a team of ethnic and cultural diversity,
- 3) Able to communicate across cultures,
- 4) Experience practicing engineering in a global context, whether through an international internship, a service learning opportunity, a virtual global engineering project or some other form of experience.
- 5) Effectively deal with ethical issues arising from cultural or national differences.

In addition, the qualities of an inter-culturally competent person include an open minded attitude, the acquisition of culture sensitive knowledge, and appropriate and effective interaction skills [2].

The course contents and related learning activities are selected, structured and developed to foster these important attributes and qualities in our students. They are centered around five themes: Understanding Yourself and Others, Developing Effective Teams, Cultural Differences, Dealing with Conflict & Team Motivation, and Cultures in Organizations. Throughout the semester students are invited to enlarge their view on the subjects by reading two text books: *Cultures and Organizations*, by Hofstede, Hofstede, and Minkov provides knowledge content on dimensions of culture, cultures and organizations, and the evolution of culture [3] and *Kiss, Bow, or Shake Hands* by Morrison and Conaway provides additional content related to conducting business in 60 countries and serves as a reference book for future travel [4].

The course incorporates a major experiential learning project, in which the students link the course contents with a concrete engineering problem in the global world. The students, in mixed teams across the ocean, encounter virtual, cross-cultural challenges of different languages, time zones, engineering backgrounds, etc. and resolve them while applying several course concepts. In this interdisciplinary project students combine their engineering knowledge and entrepreneurial spirit with their

professional and intercultural skills in order to find innovative and feasible business opportunities.

Gradual improvements on the course format

We describe hereafter a process of continuous improvement of the course since its first run, based on (yearly) feedback from the students and our own reflections as teachers. This process could be linked to recurrent cycles of using the ADDIE³ instructional design model, although the different steps are not always taken explicitly.

First run

A first edition of the course was offered in the Fall 2015 term [5]. The course format consisted of synchronous videoconference lectures twice a week given by faculty from both institutions and by guest speakers from the corporate and academic world, complemented by readings, case studies, individual assignments and group discussions. A limited number of students participated in this edition, i.e. six students at both sides.

At the end of the course, an informal student evaluation was performed. Students felt that the course material was relevant to their future work as an engineer, that the assessment methods were fair and that the course material (text books, lesson notes, and online materials) helped them understand the course contents (although a better job in organizing and presenting the material could have done). Students indicated that there was a need for less material covered in class. They were a bit frustrated about the group work done in the virtual class time, and would have rather preferred more time for discussions. Nevertheless, students loved it: “The interaction between the two universities made the class a great learning environment. By far the best experience.”, and called it an intensive, but rewarding ‘real life’ learning experience across several borders.

Also the teaching team had to cope with intercultural challenges due to different educational settings and paradigms, e.g. dealing with staggered time-zones and academic calendars (semesters are misaligned by about 4 weeks), with assessing students on a level playing field (marks are interpreted differently in the two academic worlds), with solving occasional technical hiccups, etc. One of the actions that helped the instructor team to overcome some of these difficulties was a face-to-face meeting prior to the start of the first edition of this course, where we could work out the schedule, lecture content, learning activities, and other administrative items. Such a face-to-face meeting was unfortunately not possible with the students.

Second run

A second run of the course was offered in the Spring 2017 term, again with a limited number of students (11 at KU Leuven, of which 3 Italian exchange students, and 5 at PSU).

³ ADDIE is short for Analyze, Design, Develop, Implement, and Evaluate.

In order to free up class time for more in-class interactivity and discussion, the PSU teaching team, especially the second author of this paper, managed to develop a fully online course, complete with online learning materials, activities and assignments. In this exercise more emphasis was put on globalization and its impact on engineering, and on examining differences between stereotypes and generalizations applied to personality type as well as cultural dimensions. Care was also taken to make sure learning activities and assignments were tied more closely with the course project, in a coherent way to meet the course objectives.

At PSU, the students were engaged only in online learning, while the students at KU Leuven were offered a combination of face-to-face and online learning (i.e. blended learning) in a flipped classroom model. Students at KU Leuven met now for only one session a week. Each week they were supposed to study the online material (kindly made available to them through the PSU learning platform) and one student in particular prepared the face-to-face class discussion about the topic. They were free to organize themselves for the discussion: some prepared several statements based on the course contents that could spark a discussion, some prepared a role play to let their peers experience the concepts, some prepared a short quiz as basis for a debate, etc.

The students, at KU Leuven, were very enthusiastic about the online material and the flipped classroom model. They loved the variety of preparations and discussion formats, especially because that allowed them to be more creative and helped them to better grasp the different course topics. They were a bit less happy with the instructor (first author of this paper) taking over from the student who prepared for the session and leading the discussion himself.

As no changes were made on the substantial project work as part of the course, and since the PSU students were all online students (they did not participate in the class discussions), students at KU Leuven strongly recommended at the end of the course to include a couple of formal webconferencing sessions in the beginning in order to get to know each other, and to establish better bonds between the KU Leuven and PSU students.

Third run

The third edition of this course was offered in the Spring 2018 term, now with 8 students at KU Leuven (of 5 nationalities, speaking 6 native languages), and 6 students at PSU (of 5 nationalities).

This time we adopted the flipped classroom model at both sides, i.e. students were supposed to study the online material on a weekly basis and each week one student prepared the class discussion, now set up as a webconference (using Skype for Business). Due to the different academic calendars, students at PSU already started 4 weeks ahead of the students in Leuven, and had no Easter break: that were the weeks that they prepared their class discussions only for them. The KU Leuven students prepared for the webconferencing sessions in the common part of the course, i.e. for the other weeks in the term/semester.

An interesting aspect of this run of the course was with regard to language. As it is widely accepted throughout the world in international business practice the common language in our joint class is English. Already in the first edition, students from PSU, for whom English is the official language of education (and in most cases also their mother tongue), found this in unbalance with their peers from KU Leuven. To bridge that gap, they asked to learn a few words in Dutch (the mother tongue of the majority of the students in Leuven). Therefore we started the common sessions always with a short 'language lesson'. In this third run, we continued this exercise, but because this time there was a huge diversity of students in terms of nationalities and hence languages, it was not possible to teach Dutch to the American students. Instead we ended up with short introductions to the different cultures of the students, rather than real language lessons. Students were keen to prepare a presentation about their country and were curious to learn about the cultures of others. However, we were spending quite some time on this, and the real language lesson was, as could be expected, rather limited: one could wonder whether students were learning anything about the language at all. More information on this language issue in this course has been reported in [6].

As with regard to assignments and the project work, no changes were made for this edition of the course, except that clearer instructions were given to the KU Leuven students about 'homework'. In previous editions students at KU Leuven were complaining about weekly deadlines for (small) assignments to be submitted. Although this brings added value to the course, especially when studying the online learning material, this is a not so common practice at KU Leuven, where graduate students are exposed to more autonomous learning, i.e. they take their own responsibility on how and when to study. A compromise with the PSU approach needed to be elaborated, and boiled down to mandatory assignments affecting the team work, and optional (but strongly recommended) assignments for individual learning.

Fourth run

The fourth run of this course is offered in the Spring 2019 term, with 8 students at KU Leuven (2 nationalities, and 2 native languages), and 5 students at PSU (5 nationalities, and 4 nationalities). No worth mentioning changes have been made to the course format, assignments nor project work. The only alteration made was the integration of the language lessons in the online environment, linked to the countries studied in the modules of the course, rather than to the student backgrounds. We now also use Zoom as technology for the webconferencing sessions.

Content wise some improvements were made in this edition. We added the IDI (the intercultural development inventory) and an IDI plan, where students developed a plan for their own intercultural development. At the end of the semester they (will) write a reflection paper on this activity. We also added four (new) online journal entries with cultural scenarios that required students to apply what they learned to make a recommendation in a work setting.

As this edition is still running at the time of submission of this paper, no evaluation can be provided yet.

CONCLUSION

This paper presents an example of a course that gives engineering students an opportunity to acquire the competences they will need when living and working in a global community across cultures and nations. The course is developed jointly by the Penn State University (US) and KU Leuven (Belgium). It enables future engineers to have broad engineering skills and know-how, be flexible and mobile, and be able to communicate, collaborate and interact in an international environment. This course runs now since 2015, and in consecutive editions we have fine-tuned its contents, the learning activities and its format, based on the (informal) student evaluations and feedback. In the paper we describe how we currently apply a flipped classroom model, in which each week the students study one of the online modules and come prepared to the face-to-face webconferencing sessions. Each week students rotate responsibility for leading such a virtual classroom discussion. The course also incorporates substantial project work, that students work on in mixed virtual teams, using their own choice of communication and collaboration tools, tackling challenges of different languages, time zones, engineering backgrounds, etc. All these elements contribute to the goal of enhancing and enriching the intercultural and international learning experiences for the students (and for the teachers).

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Parkinson, "The Rationale for Developing Global Competence" Online Journal for Global Engineering Education, vol 4:2, Article 2, September, 2009.
- [2] D.K. Deardorff, "The SAGE Handbook of Intercultural Competence" SAGE Publications, Inc. Thousand Oaks, California, 2009.
- [3] G. Hofstede, G.J. Hofstede, and M. Minkov, "Cultures and Organizations, Software of the Mind", McGraw Hill, 3rd ed., 2010.
- [4] T. Morrison and W.A. Conaway, "Kiss, Bow, or Shake Hands", Adams Media, Avon, MA, 2nd ed. 2006.

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- [5] W. Van Petegem, A. Erdman, D. Lang and A. Gordon, “Professional and Intercultural Engineering Competencies. Learning across borders.”, SEFI Annual Conference Proceedings, 2016, Tampere (Finland).
 - [6] D. Lang, W. Van Petegem, A. Erdman, and M. Handley, “Incorporating Language Lessons in an Engineering Across Cultures and Nations Graduate Course”, at Plenary: “Linking Languages with Engineering across Borders”, 21st annual colloquium on international engineering education, 2018, Newport, Rhode Island.